

Self-healing structural composites with electromagnetic functionality

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ABSTRACT

We have incorporated arrays of conductive electromagnetic scattering elements such as straight copper wires and copper coils into polymer based fiber-reinforced composites, resulting in materials with required structural and electromagnetic functionality. For the matrix material, we are considering a newly developed polymer in which microcracks can heal, reversibly and at the molecular level, through the application of moderate heat and pressure. This polymer is produced via Diels-Alder reaction by combining a stoichiometric ratio of 4 furan with 3 maleimide groups. The DA reaction forms cross-linked bonds throughout the polymer backbone, which by design are the weakest covalent bond in the backbone. Upon excessive loading, these bonds break preferentially and thus serve as cracking sites in the material. This de-bonding process is thermally reversible and hence the resulting cracks can be healed at the molecular level by heating. The conductive wires embedded in the composites can be used as resistive elements to heat the material, and furthermore act as electrical conductors to tune the electromagnetic properties of the system. Multifunctional composites of this kind enhance the role of structural materials from mere load-bearing systems to lightweight structures of good thermo-mechanical attributes that also have electromagnetic and other functionalities. In this paper we present an overview of our multifunctional concept, and focus on recent results pertaining to simulation and experiments of the heating functionality of the wires.

Keywords: artificial dielectric; electromagnetic scattering; multifunctional composite; self-healing; resistive heating

INTRODUCTION

Multifunctional materials, in the context of our research, integrate other functions into materials that foremost have outstanding structural integrity. We seek to develop structural composite materials with controlled electromagnetic properties such as a tunable index of refraction and RF absorption, among others. This is achieved through integration of arrays of metallic scattering elements into fiber-reinforced polymer composites, such that the arrays act as inductive structures with a plasma-like response to control the electric permittivity. As a result for instance, the dielectric constant may be tuned to negative or positive values. These structures arise from earlier work by Pendry et al.¹⁻³ and Smith et al.⁴⁻⁶ on artificial plasmon media. Another paper by our group, entitled "Metallic Coil-Polymer Braid Composites: I. The Numerical Modeling and Chirality", is also included in this conference and provides more theoretical description of the electromagnetic functionality.

As an example, we have introduced arrays of thin, straight wire into various types of composite materials. Composite panels were made by hand-layup of pre-impregnated woven fabric (prepreg) around arrays of embedded copper wire of diameter 50-100 μm . Depending on the desired plasma frequency, the wires

are periodically spaced to form a square lattice and repeated through the thickness of the composite. A representative dispersion relation of the dielectric constant in the microwave regime for one of these panels is given in Figure 1, which compares both numerical predictions with the experimental results. This graph shows the characteristic trend of changing the dielectric constant from negative to positive values as a result of the embedded plasmon media. Results for other host materials show similar behavior though the turn-on frequency is shifted depending on the host material and the wire diameter and spacing. Further details on the experimental results from these tests are reported elsewhere.⁷

Figure 1. [Top Left] Layup tool used for fabrication of the fiber reinforced composites. Prepreg layers are stacked in this device and encase wires strung around peripheral rods with the prescribed spacing. [Top Right] Schematic of thin wire array; wires are arranged horizontally and vertically in the plane and repeat through the thickness of the panel. [Lower Left] Numerical and experimental characterization of Cyanate Ester/Quartz composite panel with 0.002" diameter copper wires spaced 0.125" apart in a square array. "Turn-on" indicates the transition between the stop-band and pass-band, or the frequency above which the material transmits electromagnetic radiation. [Lower Right] The incident side of the anechoic chamber used for microwave transmission measurements through the panel.

Similarly we have made composite samples with arrays of thicker wire (254 μm diameter) to achieve the same effect. To obtain an equivalent amount of inductance as the thin wire structures, we increase the length of wire per unit volume by introducing a loop. Essentially this creates a coil of either left-handed or right-handed sense. These loops are processed into composites by textile braiding that intertwines the wire with reinforcing fiber tows. These braided elements are subsequently woven into fabric with other braids and tows of fiber and impregnated with polymer matrix. The details of composite samples made by this technique are given in another paper by our group, entitled "Metallic Coil-Polymer Braid Composites: II. Material Processing and Characterization", also presented at this conference.

Integration of these elements has introduced other opportunities for multifunctionality, most notably self-healing and thermal transport functionalities. The healing functionality arises from a recently developed polymer by Xiangxu et al.⁸ This polymer has the unique ability to heal internal damage by means of its thermo-reversible covalent bonds. As a result, cracking that may occur inside the material can be healed through the application of mild heat to repair the interface and restore the material to a majority of its former strength. When this polymer is combined with our electromagnetic wire medium, this composite has tremendous potential for further multifunctionality. The wires may serve not only as electromagnetic scattering elements, but may further provide channels through which heat is transported to heal cracks within the material. They may be heated resistively if connected to an external current source, or they may act as inductive heaters if external magnetic fields are applied. Since the wires are distributed periodically throughout the composite, heat is also uniformly distributed. There is further synergy with the fiber reinforcement of the composite such that the reinforcing fibers may also contribute to the healing mechanism. If a fiber with a negative coefficient of thermal expansion, such as para-aramid (Kevlar®) or PBO (Zylon®), is chosen to reinforce the composite laminate, then it may provide compression to close the crack faces as the material is being heated. Upon heating, a cracked polymer matrix (with a positive CTE) will expand as the reinforcing fibers contract, thus putting the matrix into compression and closing the crack faces.

Figure 2. Schematic of self-healing multifunctional concept. [Left] Fiber reinforcement contains integrated wires through braiding and/or weaving for electromagnetic and heating functionality. [Center] Braids are woven into fabric and embedded in healable polymer matrix. [Right] Woven layers are laminated into structural composite. Internal damage, in the form of polymer matrix cracking, may be repaired when heat is applied through the wires. Crack faces will close as matrix expands and fibers contract, while thermally induced healing mechanism of polymer repairs the damage.

SELF-HEALING FUNCTIONALITY

To serve as the matrix for our fiber composite we are incorporating a novel polymer developed by Xiangxu et al. into our braided composite.⁸ The ability of this material to repair broken bonds is a result of the presence of a Diels-Alder adduct in the backbone of the polymer. The material is formed by the polymerization of a furan monomer with a maleimide monomer via a Diels-Alder reaction (Figure 3). The furan joins to the maleimide through the bond labeled by the dotted arrow, and the resulting polymer unit is shown to the right. We refer to this polymer as 3M4F polymer, indicating 3 maleimide and 4 furan groups per polymer unit. The healing mechanism is also a result of the DA reaction since most DA reactions are thermally reversible. The weakest bond in the polymer structure is the polymerization/cross-linking bond of the DA adduct. While strong in comparison to other types of chemical bonds, this is the first bond to break when the material is loaded to failure or heated above its transition temperature. However, because this bond is reversible, this is also the bond that reforms when

the material is cooled below the transition temperature. Due to the highly cross-linked structure of this polymer, its mechanical properties are similar to epoxies and other thermoset resins commonly used in fiber composites.

In addition to healing demonstrations performed by Xiangxu, we have also observed the healing mechanism in samples of 3M4F polymer. Our aim was to arrest crack growth prior to complete fracture of the sample. In this way we could improve the ability to match the severed interfaces back to their original location prior to heating. Due to the inherent high mechanical strength of this material a controlled cracking procedure was devised. Samples were machined to 0.25'' x 0.15'' x 0.20'' dimensions with a 0.08'' diameter hole penetrating through the middle. Two notches were cut into the hole to initiate the crack on opposing sides of the hole. The samples were cooled in liquid nitrogen and immediately loaded in compression in the direction of the machined notch. The applied load caused cracks to grow from the notches in a controlled manner in the direction of the applied load. Cracked samples were then placed in a spring device that applied compression normal to the crack faces so as to put the crack faces in contact. Heat was then applied at various levels and durations. For samples treated for at least 6 hours above 80°C under a nitrogen atmosphere with about 8 kPa of compression normal to the interface, the crack was observed to disappear, indicating healing. In these cases, no visible scar remained, apart from the initial starter notch. These tests were only qualitative in nature. Quantitative tests of the healing efficiency are being developed. However, it appeared that the crack had been completely repaired and visually the material had been restored to its original state. Figure 3 shows representative photographs before and after the healing event.

Figure 3. [Top] Chemical reaction of furan monomer (1) with maleimide monomer (2) to form 3M4F polymer (3). Dotted arrow indicates thermally reversible DA adduct (adapted from Xiangxu et al.⁸) [Bottom] Optical photographs taken at 20X magnification of representative 3M4F sample. Diagonal view is shown of sample with pre-drilled hole and starter notches. [Left] 3M4F polymer sample after controlled cracking. Note cracks have propagated from the starter notches to the left and right of the sample. [Right] Same sample after healing for 6 hours under nitrogen and about 8kPa of compression normal to the crack face. Crack faces have disappeared leaving only starter notches and pre-drilled hole visible.

HEATING FUNCTIONALITY

Embedded wires are currently used for resistive heating as a method of welding thermoplastic polymers and polymer composites.⁹⁻¹¹ Similarly, embedded heating elements have been used to cure the resin matrix in thermoset polymer composites.^{12,13} Hence we now explore the use of our embedded wires to function as heating elements to activate healing in our composite material. We have visually demonstrated healing of internal cracking of the 3M4F polymer at a temperature of 80°C. Therefore we now see if the wire arrays in our composites, with the typical diameter and spacing used for electromagnetic functionality, are capable of heating the panel to the healing temperature.

The thin copper wires in our composite can be connected to a DC electrical source and leveraged as heating elements, dissipating heat as a result of Ohm's Law:

$$P = VI = I^2R = V^2/R \quad (1)$$

where P is power, V is voltage across the circuit element, I is DC current through the circuit, and R is the resistance of the circuit element. We first study this scheme in the finite element computer simulation software NISA and then verify our results through experimental testing. The heat transfer module of NISA, known as NISA/HEAT, uses finite element methods to solve the heat conduction equation for temperature based on a set of initial and boundary conditions.

Our thin wire arrayed composites typically have a spacing of 0.125" (3.175 mm) between copper wires of 100µm diameter. To simulate this geometry in NISA's graphical interface, a unit cell of 0.125" x 0.125" is constructed to represent a cross-section of the composite as shown in Figure 4. To reduce calculations to a 2-D problem, the unit cell is assumed to have unit depth and a constant cross-section along the length of the wire.

Figure 4. Unit cell geometry for NISA simulation of resistive heating scheme.

A square element mesh is applied to the unit cell, with the circular cross-section of wire approximated by a square pattern of 4 elements. Boundary conditions are prescribed on the mesh based on: thermal conductivity, mass, density and specific heat of the material; electrical power input and heat generation; and conditions at the edges of the unit cell. We approximate the thermal properties of the 3M4F polymer with those of DGEBA epoxy, since the two are similar in mechanical properties, and our current electromagnetic panels are fabricated with epoxy matrix. These properties are prescribed on the polymer elements of the mesh, while the properties of annealed copper are prescribed on the wire elements. It is

assumed that the electrical power input is constant over time and converted fully into heat, so a constant heat generation is prescribed on the wire elements. The conditions at the edges of the unit cell are either “insulated,” implying that boundaries of zero heat flux are prescribed on all edges of the cell, or “exposed to air,” where convection boundary conditions are prescribed on two opposite edges of the cell instead of zero heat flux. The insulated condition simulates a unit cell surrounded on all sides by identical material through periodic boundary conditions.

According to the results of our simulation, the temperature of the insulated unit cell increases linearly for a constant power input, while the temperature of the exposed unit cell holds constant after a period of time (Figure 5). Also, the temperatures at different locations in the exposed unit cell vary by as much as 15°C, as shown by the multiple lines on the graph. For the insulated unit cell, the temperature distribution differs by 4°C at the most. The power density value (W/cm^2) in these graphs denotes power distribution over the flat area of the composite panel, *not* the power distribution over the cross-section.

Figure 5. Simulated temperature vs. time response for insulated and exposed unit cells. Multiple lines indicate temperatures at various locations within the panel.

A sample composite panel was fabricated from glass-fiber reinforced epoxy prepreg and 100- μm copper wire to test the resistive heating process. Copper wires were strung in a parallel arrangement in one direction and 3 thermocouple wires were included at various depths between the prepreg layers to monitor internal temperatures. The dimensions of the panel were 15cm x 15cm x 0.32cm thick and its fiber volume fraction was around 60%. After curing, the copper wire strands that protruded from the edges of the panel were retained since they provided electrical connection.

The wires in the composite panel were combined into a single circuit by a custom apparatus we refer to as a conductor frame. The frame consists of conductor bars to which adhesive copper strips are attached. By clamping groups of wires to the conductor bars, a combined series-parallel circuit through the entire panel is created (Figure 6). The copper strips extend around the sides of the upper conductor bar so that they may be connected to the power source.

48 wires in composite =
12 sets in series, 4 wires in parallel per set

Figure 6. [Left] Composite panel in conductor frame. Embedded thermocouple wires protrude to the right of the panel. [Right] Abbreviated circuit diagram.

The DC power source used in these tests was a voltage generator with maximum output of 36 V and 8 A. In addition, the thermocouple wires were connected to a multi-channel thermocouple monitor. To measure the electrical power input, two multimeters were included in the setup to measure total voltage across all wires in the composite and total current across the entire circuit.

The voltage for our initial tests was based on simulation and remained constant throughout each individual test. The voltage was then iteratively optimized in subsequent tests to achieve our target temperature. Prior to turning on the power source the initial temperature for all thermocouple channels was recorded. Once power was supplied to the composite panel, temperatures were recorded for each of the thermocouple wires at 30-second intervals. The voltage and current were also recorded every 30 seconds for a total duration of about 20 minutes.

Non-insulated test conditions were conducted with the panel configuration as shown in Figure 6. To test insulated conditions, sheets of cotton-like fiberglass were placed on both sides of the panel to minimize heat loss.

Figure 7. Temperature vs. time for insulated [left] and exposed [right] panels.

The results of the resistive heating tests are qualitatively similar to the results of the finite element simulations. The temperature for an insulated composite rises almost linearly, while the temperature in the exposed composite rises quickly at first before holding constant (Figure 7). However, the quantitative results differ noticeably between simulation and experiment. For insulated conditions, the temperature after 1200 seconds is above 300°C in simulation, whereas the temperature in the actual test only exceeds 80°C. This error is less pronounced for the exposed case; the simulation predicts a maximum constant temperature of 70°C while the test results have a maximum temperature of 84°C. However, the simulation of exposed conditions predicts a local temperature difference of 15°C between different areas in the composite, while this temperature difference is only about 5°C in the actual test.

The tests were carried out for different levels of electrical power, and a linear correlation was found between the final temperature and the power input (Figure 8). Power density over the face of the panel is used in place of total electrical power so that the value is normalized for any size of composite panel. Temperature rise is used in place of the actual final temperature so that temperature results are normalized for any initial temperature. According to the graphs, an insulated panel requires about 60% less power than the exposed panel to reach the same temperature. If an ambient temperature of 20°C is assumed, and our target temperature is 80°C, then a temperature increase of 60°C is desired, which corresponds to 0.073 W/cm² power input for the insulated panel, compared to the exposed panel's 0.20 W/cm².

Figure 8. Temperature rise vs. power density for insulated [left] and exposed [right] panels.

Inconsistencies in the test results can be attributed to heat and electrical losses. Firstly, it is assumed that all electrical power is converted into heat, which does not reflect the energy losses that occur in reality. However, it is difficult to measure and control the exact heat energy supplied to the composite, hence we control the electrical power. Also, it is assumed that the power input remains constant as long as the voltage from the generator is constant. In reality, the increasing temperature of the composite wires increases their resistance, which in turn causes the power input to drop over time. This effect can be seen in Figure 4 for the insulated panel, where the temperature vs. time plot (which should be linear) “levels out” slightly as time progresses. The insulation used in testing is also not a perfect insulator; rather than creating a zero heat flux boundary at the composite surface, it simply absorbs the heat and traps it. In fact, at higher temperatures (60°C or more), the insulation itself becomes noticeably warmer, which indicates that it has taken some heat away from the composite rather than reflecting it back into the material.

CONCLUSIONS

We have presented the concept of a self-healing structural composite with integrated electromagnetic and self-healing functionalities. The self-healing functionality is achieved through contributions from all components, including the thermo-reversible covalent bonds of the 3M4F polymer, the thermal transport of the wires, and the compression provided by the reinforcing fibers. Thermal tests indicate that our thin wire arrays are capable of heating the composite uniformly to the healing temperature of the polymer. Future research will test the heating characteristics of our coil array design and investigate other methods of heating wires such as inductive heating.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank Fred Wudl and Xiangxu Chen of University of California, Los Angeles, for sharing their expertise on making the 3M4F material and for providing samples. This research is supported by ARO DAAD19-00-1-0525 to the University of California, San Diego.

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